

Human dignity and the best interest of the child

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Abstract:

In our daily medical practice, we are constantly facing situations that require a comprehensive view of the patient, based not only on scientific knowledge, but also encompassing relevant legal, anthropological, philosophical, and sociological concepts. This can be summarized by saying that bioethical knowledge and training are critical in current professional practice. This will allow us to provide quality care while contributing to a paradigm change in health sciences.

The objective of this presentation is to review concepts such as person, dignity, and best interests of the child, and reflect on the importance we give to them in our professional practice.

Key words: dignity, human rights, child, defense of the child

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